

Gimnastika zallarning talablari va sport zallar xususiyatlari.

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Atatsiya: Jismoniy tarbiyada gimnastika alohida o'rin tutadi, bu umumiy jismoniy ivojlanish va insonning asosiy harakat qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashni ta'minlaydi. Gimnastika o'ziga xos muammolarni eng muvaffaqiyatli hal qilish uchun keng koniyatlar yaratadigan turli xil mashqlar bilan ajralib turadi. Pedagogik vazifalar. Turli gimnastika turlari bo'yicha mashg'ulotlar hal qilishga yordam beradi eng muhim vazifalardan biri jismoniy tayyorgarlikni ta'minlashdir jismoniy va ma'naviy quvvati barkamol rivojlangan kuchli yosh avlod.

Kalit so'z: Gimnastika, halqalar, uzuklar, trampilin, gimnastika gilami.

Gimnastika - bu maxsus tanlangan jismoniy mashqlar tizimi salomatlikni yaxshilash, uyg'un jismoniy tarbiya va insonning harakat qobiliyatini, uning uchini, epchilligini, tezligini, chidamliligini, moslashuvchanligini oshirishda o'llaniladigan mashqlar, uslubiy usullar.

Gimnastika ko'pkurashning bir necha turlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bunga quyidagilar kiradi: erkaklar uchun - pol mashqlari, mashqlar pommel ot, halqalar, notekis panjaralar, gorizontalar bar, tonoz; ayollar uchun - tayanch, notekis barlarda mashqlar, muvozanat nurlari va zamin mashqlari. Sinfga badiiy gimnastika badiiy mashqlarni o'z ichiga oladi gimnastika, xoreografiya, akrobatika. Gimnastika - Olimpiya sporti. Uning mamlakatimizda rivojlanishiga rahbarlik qilmoqda gimnastika federatsiyasi

Sport zallari uchun gigienik talablar va ishlash qoidalari

Gimnastika mashg'ulotlari odatda maxsus jihozlangan gimnastika zallarida o'tkaziladi. Sport zallarida jihozlar uchun yordamchi xonalar, trenerlar va o'qituvchilar uchun xonalar, echinish xonalari (erkaklar, ayollar), shuningdek, dush va hojatxonalar (hojatxonalar) talab qilinadi. Zallardan foydalanish uchun gigienik talablar

1. Zal va uning yordamchi xonalarini bezash oson tozalanishi kerak.
2. Isitish moslamalari panjara bilan qoplangan.
3. Zaldagi harorat - 18-20 ° S (namlik - 50-60%).
4. Shamollatish tabiiy va sun'iy. 5. Derazalarning yorug'lik maydoni zamin maydonining kamida 1/5 qismini tashkil qiladi.
6. Barcha binolarni muntazam tozalash kerak.

2.2. Gimnastika anjomlari va yordamchi anjomlarining xarakteristikalarini Gimnastika mashg'ulotlarida quyidagi jihozlar va sport anjomlari qo'llaniladi.

1. Gimnastika devori umumiy rivojlantiruvchi mashqlar va toqqa chiqishni bajarish uchun ishlatiladi. Uning balandligi 3 m 20 sm, kengligi 100 sm.

mashqlarda muvozanatni saqlash, urg'u berish, ko'tarilish va hokazolarda yakka tartibda va jamoaviy mashg'ulotlarda hamda ishtirokchilarning dam olishlari uchun ishlatiladi. Uning uzunligi 4 m, eni - 24 sm, balandligi - 30 sm. Skameykaning pastki qismida 5 sm kenglikdagi blok o'rnatilgan. Gimnastika skameykasi teskari burilganda, bu blokdan muvozanat mashqlarini bajarish mumkin.

3. Ko'tarilish arqonlari ship nurlari yoki maxsus konsollarda osilgan. Arqonning qalinligi 6-9 sm, uzunligi 4-6 m. Uni qo'llaringiz bilan ushlab oson bo'lishi kerak.

4. Uzunlik odatda maxsus konsollarga birlashtiriladi. Halqalar birlashtiriladigan balandlik 5 m 50 sm, halqalar orasidagi eni 50 sm, halqalarning poldan balandligi 2 m 5 sm, halqalarning diametri 18-19 sm.

5. Erkaklar panjaralari (parallel): ustunlar uzunligi - 3 m 50 sm, oval - 41-51 mm, balandligi - 1 m 60 sm - 1 m 70 sm.

6. Ayollarning parallel panjaralari (notekis balandliklar): pastki qutbning balandligi 1 m 30 sm - 1 m 50 sm, yuqori qutbning balandligi 2 m 40 sm. Barlar yigit simlari bilan mustahkamlangan.

7. Gimnastik muvozanat nuri muvozanat mashqlarini bajarish uchun ishlatiladi. Jurnalning uzunligi 5 m, kengligi 10 sm, balandligi 1 m 20 sm, qalinligi 16 sm. Boshlang'ich mashg'ulot va isinish uchun poldan 50 sm balandlikda o'rnatilgan past log ishlatiladi.

8. Sakrab ot: bo'yi (ayollar) - 1 m 10 sm - 1 m 20 sm, bo'yi (erkaklar) - 1 m 10 sm - 1 m 35 sm, eni - 36 sm, uzunligi - 1 m 60 sm.

9. Belanchak uchun ot: uzunligi - 1 m 60 sm, eni - 36 sm, balandligi - 1 m 20 sm, tutqichlar orasidagi eni - 4-44 sm, tutqich balandligi - 12 sm.

10. Gimnastik echki: bo'yi - 100-160 sm, uzunligi - 60 sm, balandligi (qalinligi) - 40 sm.

11. Krossovka: uzunligi - 2 m 40 sm, balandligi - 1 m 20 sm - 2 m 55 sm, bo'yin diametri - 28-29 sm.

12. Gimnastika ko'prigi tayanchlar, muvozanat nurlari va notekis barlarda mashqlar uchun ishlatiladi; uzunligi - 1 m 20 sm, eni - 60 sm, balandligi - 16-20 sm.

13. Trampolin: uzunligi - 1 m 20 sm - 1 m 30 sm, balandligi - 40-50 sm.

14. Gimnastika gilamchalari: uzunligi - 200 sm, eni - 1 m 20 sm, qalinligi - 60-65 mm. Murakkab mashqlarni o'rganayotganda, ko'pikli paspaslardan foydalaning.

15. Zamin mashqlari maydoni (12-12 ×m) oq chiziq bilan chegaralangan bo'lib, uning orqasida kamida 1 m chegara talab qilinadi.

16. Trampolin: uzunligi – 5 m, eni – 2 m 50 sm, balandligi – 1 m 20 sm.

Sport jihozlari

1. Gimnastika tayoqchalari: diametri 25–30 mm, uzunligi 90–110 sm.

2. Tibbiyot to'plari: diametri 31-41 sm, vazni 1-5 kg.

3. Dumbbelllar turli shakllarda bo'lishi mumkin, ularning vazni 1-5 kg.

4. Hakamlarning ko'rsatkichlari mashqlarni bajarish uchun ballarni ko'rsatish uchun mo'ljallangan.

5. Badiiy gimnastika jihozlari: sakrash arqonlari, lentalar, sharlar, halqalar, tayoqchalar va boshqalar.

Sport zallaridan yubor qoidalari va uskunalar

Sport zalida mashq qiladiganlar quyidagi qoidalarga rioya qilishlari kerak:

1) asbob-uskunalar va jihozlarga ehtiyotkorlik bilan munosabatda bo'ling, ularni darslarga mohirona tayyorlang va keyin ularni tozalang;

2) magniyga ehtiyotkorlik bilan munosabatda bo'ling va mashg'ulotlar oxirida talabalar tirgakni, parallel panjara ustunlarini, halqalarni, ot tutqichlarini magniydan tozalashlari va gilamchalarni nam mato bilan artib olishlari kerak;

3) zalda faqat sport kiyimi va poyabzalda bo'lish;

4) darslar davomida o'qituvchi (trener) ko'rsatmalariga aniq rioya qiling, do'stlaringizga yordam bering;

5) xavfsizlik qoidalarini, o'z-o'zini sug'urtalash usullarini o'rganish ;

6) zalga kirish va chiqish faqat o'qituvchining ruxsati bilan mumkin.

Gimnastika jihozlarini har kuni tekshirish va topilgan muammolarni darhol tuzatish tavsiya etiladi. Oyiga bir marta chig'anoqlarni batafsil tekshirishni amalga oshirish kerak.

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